

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF WORKING WITH INFORMATION IN IMPROVING SOCIAL-INFORMATION COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS

Muydinjanov D.R.

Teacher of the Department of Mathematics of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *For successful professional development, a specialist working in the field of pedagogy must not only have professional knowledge, skills and qualifications, but also know how to work with information, it is said that it is necessary to take into account the specific features of working with information in the improvement of socio-informational competences.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, working with information, social-information competence, professional development, professional communication, academic mobility, competence approach.*

In order to consider pedagogic specialists as specialists who know how to work with information, it is important to fill them with theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications..

For successful professional development, a specialist working in the field of pedagogy should not only have professional knowledge, skills and qualifications, but also know how to work with information.

When improving social-informational competences, it is necessary to take into account the specific features of working with information, because it is these elements of non-verbal behavior that contain most of the information in the process of interaction and often cause misunderstanding in the process of communication between representatives of different cultures.

Advantage of gaming. The game is an opportunity to use situations, new ways of communication. Because it puts before each participant the need to be a creator, subject of educational activity, knowledge activity. It certainly overcomes the monologic limitation of traditional lessons and traditional forms of education.

Using role-playing and business games, projects, trainings, getting into the subtleties of intercultural communication in the professional field, sessions aimed at developing communication skills in information classes, focusing on the choice of the goals and conditions of communication, forms of working with information depending on the change of speech makes a secret.

The use of video materials in the classroom allows students to study the field of intercultural professional communication and learn many situations that imitate the natural conditions of business communication in working with information. It gives preference to materials that reflect the specific characteristics of national mentality and communication and have a clear professional direction. This socio-information also includes films that present integrated scenarios that visually represent reality, context, and situation in verbal and non-verbal behavior. In addition, the use of real video materials allows diversification of teaching methods.

Authentic materials with a high level of reliability play an important role in teaching professional information processing. Real texts designed for people who know how to work with information to learn a specific topic arouse great interest in students.

One of the ways to optimize the learning process is the project method, which allows you to model a real situation or prepare for professional activities.

The process of modernization of higher education determines the qualitative revision of the professional training of the future specialist. Currently, the competency-based approach to education is being introduced into the education system in many countries, including Uzbekistan.

In the works of A.P. Panfilova, from the point of view of a systematic approach, depending on the level of knowledge, he distinguishes the following stages of knowledge acquisition:

- unconscious incompetence (a person does not realize that he does not know or is not able to do something);
- conscious incompetence (there is an awareness of the absence or incompleteness of specific knowledge or knowledge and skills necessary to solve practical problems);
- conscious competence (the knowledge and skills necessary to perform this type of activity have been mastered, but attention must be increased to perform them);
- unconscious competence (the ability to successfully perform work without thinking).

In this context, learning outcomes should work with information as pedagogical goals, including:

- familiarization (discovery) - familiarization with basic concepts and procedures in a certain field of knowledge;
- mastering the basics (literacy), re-explanation, the ability to describe basic concepts and procedures;
- mastery (fluency) - successful application of basic concepts and procedures in a certain field of science;
- full assimilation (mastery) is the successful application of basic concepts and procedures in the field, as well as helping others to improve and strengthen knowledge and skills.

Graduates of higher education organizations should have not only professional knowledge, skills, and qualifications, but also general and social culture, which is the basis of a tolerant way of life of people. In this regard, the problem of improving students' social and informational competences is undoubtedly of great importance in the activities of higher education organizations.

The goals of teaching work with information to improve students' social-informational competences are:

- to cultivate respect for the spiritual values of the culture of other nations;
- intercultural communication, development of readiness for active social and cultural events.

Social-informational activity acts as the interaction of people in the creation, development, preservation and distribution of cultural values of social importance in modern society.

Axborotlar bilan ishlash yordamida bu dunyoning o'zaro bog'liqligi va yaxlitligini, insoniyatning global muammolarini hal qilishda madaniyatlararo hamkorlik zarurligini anglab yetishi orqali talabalarni shaxs sifatida tarbiyalash amalga oshiriladi.

I.A. Maskinskaya revealed and experimentally confirmed the pedagogical conditions for the formation of social and professional competences of future specialists, and also distinguishes the main directions of implementation of this process: theoretical, practical and moral-

psychological. These areas, in our opinion, take the leading place in improving the social and informational competences of their students while working with information.

The theoretical and practical analysis of the problem, the study of the experience of teaching work with information to the students of higher educational institutions of higher education organizations made it possible to form pedagogical conditions for the development of social and informational competence. Including,

- development and introduction of a model of improving students' social and informational competencies by learning to work with information in a higher education organization;
- ensuring interdependence of theoretical, practical and moral-psychological components of the process of developing students' social-informational competence;
- development and testing of diagnostic tools that allow to determine the level of development of socio-informational competence;
- organization of special work on the training of teachers of higher education organizations for the development of social and informational competence of students in the process of learning to work with information.

In the conditions of globalization, the dynamics of socio-informational competences, adaptation of communication to the needs of users and ensuring the effectiveness of communication in various spheres of human activity determine intercultural and linguistic requirements for communication.

The concept of "competitiveness" of a specialist includes the level of general culture, personal qualities and professional qualities that allow a graduate to adapt to modern requirements and realize acquired competencies.

Academic mobility, a complex and multifaceted process of intellectual and professional development, scientific and cultural potential serve students to solve life situations and analyze them from the point of view of local and foreign culture.

The development of students' social and informational competence is important from the point of view of the possibility of increasing their motivation to work with information.

Development of social and information competence based on the competence approach creates the following opportunities:

- to be able to solve problems, to study independently, to use experience, to organize one's knowledge;
- receiving and processing data;
- to express one's position in the discussion, to form one's opinion, to evaluate;
- participation in the project, being responsible, being able to organize one's own work;
- using new technologies and communications, finding new solutions.

So, competence allows to solve various problems in everyday, professional and social life. The practice of communication in working with information has shown that even in-depth knowledge of working with information cannot sometimes resolve misunderstandings and conflicts with interlocutors when working with information. In order to prepare students for effective intercultural communication, the knowledge of working with foreign information should be supplemented with cultural characteristics and intercultural knowledge.

In the theory of intercultural communication, "social-informational competences" are a set of certain knowledge, skills, and abilities common to all communicators. This term is usually associated with the concept of "communicative competence", which includes topics, tasks, and

communicative attitudes. It is understood as the experience of communication between the participants of communication. So, communicative competence means knowing how to work with information, having the ability to correlate working with information, relations between communicators, the ability to organize, encouraging communication taking into account social culture, and understanding communicative norms.

The terms "communicative competence" and "social-informational competence" are closely related. Communicative social-informational competence is interpreted as a set of special, social-informational and sociolinguistic knowledge and skills. It determines the effectiveness of interpersonal and intercultural communication to achieve professional and personal goals. It is the ability to remove communication barriers.

It is appropriate to study the description of the concepts of "compensator", "social-information compensator", "compensatory competition" in the development of students' interpersonal and intercultural communication opportunities on the basis of social-information compensator.

So, based on the analysis, it can be said that socio-informational compensators are important in the development of students' interpersonal and intercultural communication opportunities in working with information.

The development of socio-informational competence should be based on:

- to develop the ability to think about one's own and other cultures, which prepares for a positive attitude to the manifestation of another culture;
- to provide knowledge about the relevant culture for a deep understanding of the relationship between one's own and other cultures;
- to acquire knowledge about the social-informational forms of interaction accepted in one's own and other cultures.

In the interpretation of socio-informational competences, most authors emphasize that the students' knowledge of the country's culture, their similarities and differences in working with their information is not limited. In the research, socio-informational competence is also emphasized, and according to it, social-informational competence is a combination of culture, knowledge, skills, qualities and skills. Also, socio-informational competence provides communicative and non-communicative activities in the conditions of intercultural interaction.

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